

An I-Network Switched Capacitor Multilevel Inverter (INSC-MLI) Topology with Reduced Switch Count and its SV-PWM based control algorithm

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ABSTRACT

A new multilevel inverter topology which can synthesize seven levels in the voltage waveform with a voltage boost of 150% is presented in this paper. The topology is named as I- network switched capacitor multilevel inverter (INSC-MLI), since the switched capacitor network employed in the topology resembles the alphabet "I". The topology has two dc link capacitors, two floating capacitors and nine IGBT switches. The maximum blocking voltage across each of the switch employed in the inverter is less than or equal to the input dc voltage. Further the reduced switch count aids in reducing the total blocking voltage of the circuit. The voltage across the floating capacitors is self-balancing in nature and is accomplished through symmetric charging and discharging cycle. The inverter is controlled using a modified space vector modulation scheme. The performance of the topology is analysed using simulation and experimental prototypes and the results are presented.

Keywords

Active Neutral Point Clamped Inverter; Switched Capacitor Multilevel Inverter; Space Vector; Blocking Voltage.

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1. Introduction

Power Converters are the inevitable elements in all the modern electrical applications like renewable power generation, electric vehicles and their charging stations, uninterrupted power supply systems, HVDC transmission etc., [1-2]. The conventional two-level inverters employed in the above systems has limitations due to poor power quality and high voltage stress. Solid state switches with higher power rating are required to handle this high voltage stress. But the technology employed in high voltage solid state switches are yet to mature. The multilevel inverters with their ability to synthesize high terminal voltage with matured low voltage components comes as a panacea for the setbacks due to high voltage stress [3-4]. Conventionally Multilevel Inverters are classified as: 1. Diode Clamped Multilevel Inverter, 2. Flying Capacitor Multilevel Inverter and 3. Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter [5]. The Diode clamped Multilevel Inverter requires multiple diodes with different voltage ratings. This makes the circuit construction tedious. Further it comes with an inherent voltage unbalance issue, thus necessitating a dedicated auxiliary voltage balancing circuit. The voltage balancing circuit makes the circuit bulky and reduces the system's reliability [6-7]. The voltage balancing issue in Diode Clamped Multilevel Inverter topology is overcome by using the Flying Capacitor Multilevel Inverter. The redundant switching states in the flying capacitor multilevel inverter topology ensures symmetrical charging and discharging cycle to achieve voltage balancing. Developing a control algorithm and implementing it to control the said topology with multiple redundant switching states is a bit cumbersome [8-9]. The Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverters with its cascaded independent voltage sources helps to reduce the device power rating and nullify the voltage balancing issues arising due to usage of capacitors. But it requires multiple independent sources and inclusion of each dc source costs additional four switches. Thus, making the number of components employed in the circuit drastically high at higher levels [10-11].

In addition to the drawbacks discussed above, the major setback of the classical topologies is that, they are basically buck converters. So, the current research in this field is aimed at achieving the following in the multilevel inverter topologies: a) higher voltage levels with fewer switches, b) Self-voltage balancing ability in case if capacitors are used and c) voltage boosting ability. Many topologies are found in the literature which aims at changing the structure of CHB-MLI, thus reducing the number of components without trading off the benefits like modularity and simple control methods of CHB-MLI [12-15]. But all the above topologies are suitable only for low voltage applications. As for as high voltage applications are concerned their utilisation is limited due to the high voltage stress across the switches in H-Bridge [16].

The opportunities for hybridizing the classical topologies were explored to achieve the three objectives mentioned earlier. Active neutral point clamped inverters are constructed by hybridizing diode clamped multilevel inverter and flying capacitor multilevel inverter [17-19]. The ANPC topology

proposed in [20] reduces the switching stress across the switches and the maximum voltage across each switch is fifty percent of the voltage at the dc-link capacitor. It is also self-balancing in nature. But the topology cannot boost the voltage and at lighter loads it requires booster circuits to achieve voltage balancing. A five level, seven level and T-type inverter controlled by modulation strategies like SPWM, SVPWM and SHE are presented in [21-23]. An active neutral point clamped inverter connected in series with an auxiliary flying capacitor unit is proposed in [24]. The topology uses a model predictive control to balance the capacitor voltage due to the absence of redundant switching states. This makes the control complex. An improved hybrid nine level inverter topology is presented in [25]. It proposes a look up table-based control algorithm utilising the redundant switching states to achieve capacitor voltage balancing. But the peak voltage delivered at its terminals is less than or equal to the input dc voltage in all the topologies addressed in [21-25].

The concept of switched capacitor is applied in the hybridization of diode clamped and flying capacitor multilevel inverters [26-27]. This hybridization enables the multilevel inverter topologies to attain voltage boosting and self-voltage balancing capabilities with fewer switches. A switched capacitor-based diode clamped multilevel inverter is proposed in [28]. This topology is capable of synthesizing five levels and can be extended if a greater number of levels is required. The number of switches and capacitors employed in the topology is quite high even though it can achieve self-voltage balance and voltage boost. The concept of switched capacitor is also employed in H-bridge based topologies to achieve the goals of multiple voltage levels with fewer switch count, self-balancing ability and voltage boost. A switched capacitor cell, which can be connected in series parallel combinations to attain multiple levels in the voltage is proposed in [29]. Here a H-Bridge is used for polarity reversal. But the addition of every capacitor in to the circuit results in addition of three more components. Thus, making the circuit bulky.

A switched capacitor-based H-Bridge unit is presented in [30] for high frequency applications, but the multiple H-Bridges increase the number of switches drastically. A topology with the same concept of switched capacitor unit combined with a H-Bridge for polarity reversal is suggested in [31]. But the switches connected in the H-Bridge have to withstand a voltage which is twice the input voltage. Further for high voltage applications, five switches are to be replaced with switches which has two IGBTs connected in series. A single stage switched capacitor module for cascaded operation is presented in [32]. The boost factor of the topology is two. But it can deliver nine levels in the output voltage with peak inverse voltage across all the switches less than the magnitude of input voltage. It requires 12 switches to synthesize nine levels. A compact switched capacitor multilevel inverter with self-voltage balancing and voltage boosting characteristics is proposed in [33]. Further a parabola carrier signal-based level shifted PWM for controlling the topology is addressed. It requires 11 IGBTs to produce eleven levels in the terminal voltage. A family of switched capacitor inverters capable of

giving seven levels in the output voltage with a boost factor of 1.5 is proposed in [34]. It can deliver seven levels with 10 IGBTs.

A hybrid multilevel converter topology is proposed. The salient contributions of this article are follows

- The concept of switched capacitor is used in the hybridization of diode clamped and flying capacitor multilevel inverter topology.
- the proposed topology has both self-voltage balancing and voltage boosting ability. The voltage gain attained is 1.5.
- It requires only nine switches to deliver seven levels and the voltage boost, when compared to the topology presented in [26], which requires 10 switches for delivering the same voltage levels and voltage boost.
- The total blocking voltage of the topology is less when compared to the similar topologies in recent literature.

2. Construction and operation of the proposed topology

The basic unit of INSC-MLI is shown in Figure 1. The “I” shaped switching network ABCDEF, which gave the name for this topology is highlighted. There are two capacitors with common neutral in the left-hand side of the dumbbell network acting as a dc-link and two floating capacitors in its right. For a given input dc voltage of V_{in} , the topology delivers an alternating voltage with a peak of $1.5V_{in}$ with four steps 0 , $0.5V_{in}$, V_{in} and $1.5V_{in}$ at its terminals. The floating capacitors act as switched capacitors. They get charged during first two steps and discharge the voltage during next two steps.

Figure 1. Proposed I-Network Switched Capacitor Multilevel Inverter (INSC-MLI)

2.1. Charging of capacitors C_3 and C_4

While synthesizing zero state, the capacitors C_3 and C_4 gets charged to a voltage of $0.5V_{in}$ while the multilevel inverter topology is operating in zero state, the charging current path is as shown in the Figure 2. The switches S_1 , S_2 , S_3 and S_4 are in ON state. This makes the voltage between points E and G, as Zero according to KVL. The freewheeling path for the load current during the zero state will be attained through the loop “bcdm hij”, by closing the switch S_5 as shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conduction paths during zero state

The step $0.5V_{in}$ is obtained in the waveform by making the switches S_1 , S_3 , and S_6 to conduct. The direction of flow of load current is shown in the Figure 3a. Here, the voltage across the capacitor C_1 appears across the load. The negative step $-0.5V_{in}$ is obtained by making the voltage across capacitor C_2 to appear across the load through the conduction of S_2 , S_4 , and S_7 as shown in Figure 3b. During both the positive and negative states, the capacitors C_3 and C_4 gets charged through the loop “bcdm hij”, as shown in the Figure.3.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Conduction paths during 50% of input voltage in load (a) $+0.5V_{in}$ (b) $-0.5V_{in}$

By applying Kirchoff’s voltage law to the loop “bcdefl” in [Figure.3a](#)

$$I_{LP1} = \frac{-0.5V_{in}}{(3R_S+R_L)+jX_L} \quad (1)$$

Here,

I_{LP1} – Load current while synthesizing the level +0.5Vin

R_S – Switch resistance

Similarly, while synthesizing -0.5Vin, the value of load current I_{LN1} can be estimated by applying KVL to loop “ifghj”

$$I_{LN1} = \frac{+0.5V_{in}}{(3R_S+R_L)+jX_L} \quad (2)$$

2.2. Discharging of capacitors C_3 and C_4

The voltage across the capacitors C_1 and C_4 is made to appear across the load to synthesize the step +Vin in the terminal voltage waveform. This is done by making the switches S_1, S_9, S_5 and S_7 to conduct as shown in [Figure 4a](#). The capacitor C_4 will be discharging during the process. For the negative step -Vin in the capacitors C_2 and C_3 will come in the conduction path through the switches S_2, S_9, S_3 and S_5 as shown in [Figure 4b](#). Unlike the charging state of the capacitors C_3 and C_4 , wherein charging current and load current are simultaneously flowing in the dumbbell network, only load current will be flowing during the discharging state.

Figure 4. Conduction paths during 100% of input voltage in load (a) +Vin (b) -Vin

By applying KVL in the loop “lbcihmfjl”, the load current I_{LP2} while synthesizing the level +Vin can be estimated as shown in [equation \(3\)](#)

$$I_{LP2} = \frac{-V_{in}}{(4R_S+R_L)+jX_L} \quad (3)$$

The value of load current I_{LN2} can be estimated by applying KVL to loop “lfmdcij” as

$$I_{LN2} = \frac{+V_{in}}{(4R_S+R_L)+jX_L} \quad (4)$$

The voltage step of ±1.5Vin can be obtained by making one of the two dc link capacitors and one of the two floating capacitors to conduct. The positive step is obtained through the conduction path $C_1-S_1-S_8-S_4-C_4-C_3-S_6$ as shown in [Figure 5a](#). Similarly, the negative step -1.5Vin can be obtained through the path $C_2-S_2-S_3-S_4-C_3-S_3-S_8-S_2$.

Figure 5. Conduction paths during 150% of input voltage in load (a) +1.5Vin (b) -1.5Vin

The load currents while synthesizing the levels -1.5 Vin and +1.5Vin are obtained by applying KVL to the loops “bcihmdefjl” and “lfghmdcij” shown in [Figure 5a](#) and [5b](#) respectively.

$$I_{LP3} = \frac{-1.5V_{in}}{(4R_S+R_L)+jX_L} \quad (5)$$

$$I_{LN3} = \frac{+1.5V_{in}}{(4R_S+R_L)+jX_L} \quad (6)$$

By adding the equations (1- 6), it is observed that the current through the capacitors C₁, C₂, C₃ and C₄ over a cycle is zero. This ensures the inherent voltage balancing ability of the proposed INSC-MLI.

3. Space Vector Algorithm for single phase ANPC inverter

The space vector diagram of single phase ANPC inverter is shown in Figure 6a. The reference vector is constituted by linear combination of V_a and V_b voltage vectors. The reference voltage V_{ref} can be divided into two components such as the fixed vector component V_a and rotating component V_b.

Figure 6. (a) Space vector diagram of single phase ANPC inverter
(b) Operating States spaced in a one-dimensional Plane

The reference vector with magnitude of V_{ref} and phase angle of ωt can be represented as modular input. V_{ref} is the reference voltage vector projected at α axis. The seven level single phase ANPC inverter has seven operating states and these states are spaced on an one dimensional space vector plane as shown in Figure 6b. Out of seven operating states, six of them constitutes the active state vectors and the remaining one vector corresponds to a zero state vector where the load terminals are connected to single potential point either V_{cc} or ground. The zero vector is positioned at the center of the space vector plane. Thus, the six active space vector region and resultant output voltage to each active state vector are shown in Figure 6b. The input to the ANPC inverter is V_{dc}. The reference vector V_{ref} determines the output voltage of the proposed inverter. This reference vector oscillates at the same frequency of the output voltage waveform within the six active operating regions. During these oscillations, the peak value of the reference voltage vector V_{ref} decides the maximum value of the

output voltage. The ratio between the peak value of V_{ref} and the maximum value gives the modulation index M. Modulation index is given by equation (7).

$$M = V_P/V_{dc} \quad (7)$$

where V_{dc} is the input voltage.

V_{ref} does not exceeds the operating region, if M<0.33.

3.1. Calculation of Dwelling Time

The desired voltage at the output can be obtained by the vector sum of two state vectors V_a and V_b when the V_{ref}, reference vector lies between them. This is given by equation (8)

$$V_{ref} = V_a + V_b \quad (8)$$

Let T_s be the overall sampling time period. The voltage seconds balance equation can be used to determine the switching intervals T_a and T_b.

$$V_{ref} \times T_s = V_a \times T_a + V_b \times T_b \quad (9)$$

Where,

$$T_s = T_a + T_b \quad (10)$$

By solving equation (9) and (10), the switching times T_a and T_b can be calculated. The switching times T_a and T_b representing the sector are arranged into a symmetrical sequence where the reference voltage vector is spaced. The symmetrical switching pulse pattern is shown in Figure.7.

Figure 7. Switching Pulse Pattern

The switching sequence will reduce the harmonic distortion at the produced output voltage waveform. The switching operating time for each active vector of the output voltage is shown in Table 1, where V_{dc} is the input voltage.

Table 1. Switching Operating Time of the Output Voltage

Sector (S _i)	T _a	T _b
1	$3T_s V_{ref}/V_{dc}$	$(V_{dc}-3V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$
2	$(2V_{dc}+3V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$	$(3V_{ref}-V_{dc})T_s/V_{dc}$
3	$3(V_{dc}+V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$	$(2V_{dc}+3V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$
4	$3T_s V_{ref}/V_{dc}$	$(V_{dc}-3V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$
5	$(2V_{dc}+3V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$	$(V_{dc}+3V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$
6	$3(V_{dc}+V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$	$(2V_{dc}+3V_{ref})T_s/V_{dc}$

Table 2. Switching States of each Active Vector in 7L-ANPC Multilevel Inverters

Switching States	V _o	Sector (S _i)	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9
V ₀	-1.5V _{dc}	0	0	PWM(T _a)	PWM(T _b)	0	0	1	0	0	1
V ₁	-V _{dc}	1	0	PWM(T _a)	PWM(T _b)	0	0	0	1	1	1
V ₂	-0.5V _{dc}	2	0	PWM(T _a)	0	PWM(T _b)	0	1	0	0	0
V ₃	0	3	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0
V ₄	0.5V _{dc}	4	PWM(T _a)	0	PWM(T _b)	0	1	0	0	0	0
V ₅	V _{dc}	5	PWM(T _a)	0	0	PWM(T _b)	0	0	1	1	1
V ₆	1.5V _{dc}	6	PWM(T _a)	0	0	PWM(T _b)	1	0	0	0	1

Figure 8 shows the flow chart for implementation of SVPWM based single phase ANPC Multilevel inverter in MATLAB/SIMULINK.

Figure 8. Flowchart for Implementation of SVPWM in Simulation

Using the volt second equation over a full sampling period the switching time values of T_a and T_b are determined. Table 2 shows the switching states of each active vector. In each sector, all the switches are operated at either ON or OFF conditions, while the two switches are operated at high frequency.

3.2. Determination of Sector Angle

By equating V_{ref} to the corresponding voltage levels in the sectors, the sector angles can be calculated. The remaining angles correspond to the zero state vectors. The length of the null vector has to be minimized to improve the average output voltage.

3.3. Three phase extension

The INSC-MLI can be connected in parallel with a dc source and dc link capacitors to extend for three phase applications. For three phase ANPC inverter, let the switching variables of the output state of each phase be defined as S_A, S_B and S_C and hence the output voltages can be represented as,

$$\begin{cases} V_A = S_A \cdot V_{dc} \\ V_B = S_B \cdot V_{dc} \\ V_C = S_C \cdot V_{dc} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Where V_A, V_B and V_C are the output phase voltages of the three-phase inverter, V_{dc} is the dc link voltage.

$$S_X = \{-1.5V_{dc}, -V_{dc}, -0.5V_{dc}, 0, 0.5V_{dc}, V_{dc}, 1.5V_{dc}\} \quad (12)$$

$$X = \{A, B, C\} \quad (13)$$

Figure 9. Space Vector Diagram of Seven Level Inverter

The space vector diagram of single phase seven level inverter has $(7-1)^2=36$ triangles in a sector. The switching states of n level multilevel inverter are given by n^3 . [Figure 9](#) shows the space vector diagram of 7L ANPC inverter. Hence the SVPWM strategy of ANPC inverter consists of $7^3=343$ space vector switching states, 127 space vector locations and 216 triangular sectors. In high level inverters the complexity arises in determining the correct location of reference vector, on time and the switching states. It becomes most important to provide a simple and efficient solution. The triangle in which the reference vector is located among the 36 triangles of a sector can be found by algebraic equations and the triangle is denoted as Δ_i , where $i=1 \dots 36$.

The modulation index is defined as

$$m_i = v_1 / v_{1p}$$

Where v_1 is the modulator fundamental voltage peak value, and v_{1p} is the fundamental voltage peak value at the six-step operation. The rudimentary idea behind the space vector modulation is to utilize discrete switching states and on times to compensate the required voltage-seconds. Generally, in a two-level inverter the on time can be determined by identifying the location of reference vector inside the sector S_i where $i=1$ to 6. The volt-second equation for a two-level inverter is given by,

$$V_s T_s = V_a T_a + V_b T_b \tag{14}$$

The volt-seconds equation along α_0 and β_0 axis, is given by,

$$V_{\mu 0}^s T_s = t_a + 0.5 t_b \tag{15}$$

$$V_{v 0}^s T_s = y t_b \tag{16}$$

$$T_s = t_a + t_b + t_0 \tag{17}$$

Where y ($y = \sqrt{3}/2$ (or) 0.866) denotes the height of the triangle of the Sector S_i and T_s is the total time period ($T_s=1/2f_s$), f_s is the switching frequency. Assuming that the triangles in the sector are all equilateral triangle, by solving the [equations \(15\)](#)

to [\(17\)](#), the on-time calculation can be formulated and is given by [\(18\)](#) to [\(20\)](#),

$$t_a = T_s \left[V_{\mu 0}^s - \frac{V_{v 0}^s}{2y} \right] \tag{18}$$

$$t_b = T_s \left[\frac{V_{v 0}^s}{y} \right] \tag{19}$$

$$T_s = t_a + t_b + t_0 \tag{20}$$

Let us assume that V_{ref} is the reference vector of magnitude $|V_{ref}|$, which makes an angle of γ with the μ axis. The same point is shifted to a small vector v_{ref} which makes an angle γ_0 between the axis μ_0 and v_0 . Hence, by finding the on-times of the small vector v_{ref} , the on-times of any reference vector V_{ref} can be determined. $S_i = \text{int}(\varphi/60) + 1$

The sector S_i ($1 \leq S_i \leq 6$) in which the reference vector is present and its angle γ ($0 \leq \gamma \leq 60^\circ$) within the sector for any position of reference vector is determine by [\(21\)](#) and [\(22\)](#) respectively.

$$S_i = \text{int} \left(\frac{\varphi}{60} \right) + 1 \tag{21}$$

$$\gamma = \text{rem} \left(\frac{\varphi}{60} \right) \tag{22}$$

Where ϕ ($0 \leq \phi \leq 360^\circ$) is the angle of reference vector with respect to μ axis.

In linear modulation mode, the reference vector V_{ref} moves in a circular trajectory. The reference vector tip can be found in any of the 36 triangles of a sector Δ_0 - Δ_{35} . The main objective of the proposed methodology is to employ analogy of small vector in virtual two level in order to find the triangle I which the point X of the reference vector V_{ref} is situated and to calculate the on-times of the triangles using on-time calculation of two level inverter [\(18\) – \(20\)](#).

Figure 10. Space vector of Virtual two level from Seven level inverter

The triangles existing in the sector are classified into type1 and type2 triangle. [Figure 10](#) shows the identification of reference vector V_{ref} location in the type1 and type2 triangles of the sector 1. The base side is present at the bottom side in type1 triangles. eg. Triangle Δ_8 , whereas the triangle is inverted in type2 triangles eg. triangle Δ_1 , Δ_7 . To find the triangle in

which the tip X of the reference vector V_{ref} two integers can be used which depends on its coordinates (V_{μ}, V_{ν}) as,

$$Z_1 = \text{int}(V_{\mu} + V_{\nu}/\sqrt{3}) \quad (23)$$

$$Z_2 = \text{int}(V_{\nu}/y) \quad (24)$$

Geometrically, the integer values indicate the intersection of two regions which is either a triangle or rhombus. In [Figure 10](#), for the reference vector V_{ref} , $Z_1=1$ and $Z_2=0$ the intersection is a rhombus ABDC where the tip of the reference vector is situated. The rhombus ABDC consists of two triangles Δ_7 and Δ_8 . The coordinates of reference vector V_{ref} with respect to the point A of rhombus can be written as,

$$V_{\mu i} = V_{\mu} - Z_1 + 0.5Z_2 \quad (25)$$

$$V_{\nu i} = V_{\nu} - Z_2y \quad (26)$$

The sub triangle in which the reference vector V_{ref} is situated can be identified by comparing the slope of A and AD. The slope A and AD can be written as

$$V_{\nu i} \leq \sqrt{3}V_{\mu i} \quad (27)$$

Now, by evaluating the inequality of equation (17), results in two findings on small vector v_{ref} and triangle number Δ_i . The triangle number is determined by solving the following equations (28) and (29)

$$\Delta_i = Z_1^2 + 2Z_2 \quad (28)$$

else

$$\Delta_i = Z_1^2 + 2Z_2 + 1 \quad (29)$$

The coordinates of the triangle can be determined as $(V_{\mu i}, V_{\nu i})$ and $(0.5 - V_{\mu i}, y - V_{\nu i})$. Have determined the individual μ, ν coordinates the switching state on times can be found using the equations (18) to (20).

4. Simulation results

The INSC-MLI is simulated in MATLAB Simulink environment. The IGBT switches with antiparallel diode are used for emulating S1 to S4 and S6 to S8. The switch S5 is accomplished with two IGBTs named S5a and S5b connected back to back. The parameters used for simulation is given in [Table 3](#).

For the given input voltage of 100 V and a load with impedance $Z = 30 + j15.7\Omega$, the voltage observed across the switches in the circuit is shown in [Figure 11a](#). From the figure it can be observed that at any instant the number of switches conducting in the topology varies from 4 to 5 which is one less than the number of switches in the conduction path of the topology proposed in [34]. This minimises the conduction losses of the INSC-MLI. The blocking voltage across the

switches S_{5a} and S_{5b} are observed as 50 V which is 50 % of the input voltage and from the complimentary blocking voltage waveform the bidirectional conduction of the switch S_5 is understood.

Table 3. Simulation parameters

Sl.No	Parameter	Specification
1	Capacitor rating	C1 4700 μ F
		C2 4700 μ F
		C3 4700 μ F
		C4 4700 μ F
2	Load rating	R 100 Ω (for dynamic operation) 30 Ω (for steady state operation)
		L 50 mH
3	Input voltage	100 V
4	Output voltage	150 V
5	Modulation index	0.95

(a)

Figure 11. (a) blocking voltage across the switches S₁-S₈ (from top to bottom) (b) Current through the switches S₁-S₈

The total blocking voltage across the circuit is 8 p.u, with a base of 100 V. The current through the switches S₁ to S₈ is shown in Figure 11b. The switches S₁ to S₄ in the charging loop ‘bcdmhlj’ are subjected to a current of 20 A. which is four times that of the peak current in other switches. This is due to the higher charge current drawn by the capacitors C₃ and C₄. In the switches which are outside the charging loop experiences a current flow of 4.5 A which is equal to load current. The complimentary conduction of the switches S_{5a} and S_{5b} also can be observed in the Figure 11b. The peak load voltage for the abovesaid input voltage is 150 V and the peak load current is 4.4 A. The same can be observed in the simulated load voltage and load current wave forms shown in Figure 12a. The seven steps in the load voltage waveform is clearly depicted. To test the performance of the topology under dynamic conditions, it is subjected to a sudden load addition as follows, the terminals of the INSC-MLI is connected to a pure resistive load of 100 ohm. The peak load current in that case is 1.5A as shown in Figure 12b, at 0.8 second the terminal is made to feed a load of R=30Ω and L=50 mH. The peak current in this case is 4.5A. The inverter absorbs the additional load with a current spike below

1A. Further, when the load is removed the inverter returns back to previous position seamlessly at 0.86 second as portrayed in the Figure 12b.

Figure 12. (a) Load voltage and Load Current (from top to bottom) (b) Load current during sudden load changes

During the normal operation and during the disturbances the voltage and current across the capacitors C₃ and C₄ is portrayed in Figure 13a. From the Figure 13a, it is observed that the voltage across the capacitors C₃ and C₄ is oscillating at 50 V and balanced inherently. The current through the capacitors C₃ and C₄ reaches a maximum value of 17 A which is nearly 4 times the load current.

The voltage across the capacitors C₁ and C₂ can be balanced by ensuring the proper grounding at neutral point. The current through the capacitors will also be steady as they are continuously connected to the source voltage 100 V.

Figure 13. (a) Voltage across the capacitors C_3 and C_4 (from top to bottom) (b) Current through the capacitors C_3 and C_4

Following a disturbance at 0.8 second the capacitor voltages are subjected to a slight disturbance but regained their balance as shown in [Figure 13b](#). The current during the disturbance reaches a maximum of 20 A before settling at the value of 17 A. From the capacitor current waveforms, it can also be observed that the charging current drawn by the capacitors C_3 and C_4 is influenced by load inductance.

5. Experimental Results

A 0.5 kW prototype is fabricated using C3M0120090d IGBTs. The experimental parameters are input voltage $V_{dc}=100V$, the capacitors $C_1= C_2= C_3= C_4=4700\mu F$. A switching frequency of 5KHz is used. The voltage and current rating of the abovesaid IGBT is 900 V and 23A respectively. Theoretical and simulation concepts explained in the previous sections are verified experimentally as follows. The prototype is made to operate in no load, the voltage across the terminals and the capacitors C_3 and C_4 are observed. The observed waveform is portrayed in [Figure 14a](#). From the figure it can be found that, the experimental terminal voltage is 150 V peak and the voltage across capacitors C_3 and C_4 are 50 V. The capacitor voltages are inherently balanced without the need for voltage balancing circuit. The initial voltage across the capacitors C_3 and C_4 shown in the [Figure 14b](#) which depicts the swift response of the capacitors with less transient voltage and transition time.

Figure 14. (a) Voltage across terminals of the inverter and capacitor C_3 and C_4 and no-load current (b) Voltage across the capacitors C_3 and C_4

A load of 125 ohm 50 mH is connected across the terminals and the load current is observed. [Figure 15a](#) shows a load current of 1.18 A under a voltage of 150 V. Further it can also be found that the voltage across the capacitors C_3 and C_4 remains balanced during the load conditions. To study the dynamic performance of the proposed INSC-MLI the modulation index has been changed from 0.95 to 0.75 and the results are shown in [Figure 15b](#). From the Figure it can be found that the transition during the change in modulation index is smooth.

Figure 15. (a) Voltage across terminals of the inverter and capacitor C_3 and C_4 and load current (b) Voltage across terminals of the inverter and capacitor C_3 and C_4 and load current during modulation index variation

Table 4. Comparison of INSC-MLI with recent Topologies

Topology in	Number of				Voltage boosting	Maximum blocking voltage (in p.u)	Three phase extension
	Levels	Switches	Diodes	Floating capacitors			
[17]	7	18	-	2	-	1	yes
[18]	7	12	-	1	-	1	yes
[19]	7	14	-	2	-	1	yes
[21]	5	7	2	1	-	1	yes
[22]	7	16	-	1	-	1	yes
[23]	7	8	-	1	-	1	yes
[31]	9	10	1	2	yes	2	no
[27]	9	9	2	2	yes	4	no
[28]	9	12	-	3	yes	2	no
[32]	9	12	-	2	yes	1	no
[33]	9	11	-	2	yes	1	no
[34]	7	10	-	2	yes	1	yes
Proposed	7	9	-	2	yes	1	yes

Under the modulation index of 0.75, the terminal voltage lost a level in positive and negative cycles. For a peak voltage of 100 V, the load current observed is 0.8 A under a load of 125 ohm and 50 mH.

For a blocking voltage of 50V across the switch and the load current of 1.2A the switching loads and conduction loss for the IGBTs S5a and S5b are estimated as 0.197 W and 0.213 mW respectively. The estimation was done based on the linearized switching model presented in [Rashid]. Similarly, on calculating the losses across the other switches, the net power loss was estimated 5 W. For an output power of 150 W, the efficiency of the INSC-MLI is thus computed as 96.57%. The experimental prototype developed is shown in the [Figure 16](#).

Figure 16. Experimental Prototype

The INSC-MLI is compared with the topologies presented recently in the aspects of Number of levels (N_{Level}), Number of switches (N_{switch}), Number of Diodes (N_D), voltage boosting capability and maximum blocking voltage and the observations are presented in [Table 4](#). instants and requires 5-6 switches to be in conduction at any instant to deliver seven levels.

As for as the topologies with voltage boosting ability are concerned, the SCM topology presented in [\[31\]](#) requires ten switches to synthesize 9 levels. Also, it requires 88 switching transitions per cycle to deliver nine levels. The topology in [\[32\]](#) requires 9 switches and 56 switching transitions to deliver the same nine levels. The BSC7LI discussed in [\[34\]](#) requires 34 switching. The INSC-MLI can deliver seven levels at its terminals with 32 switching instants and 4-5 IGBTs in conduction at any instant. That is, the INSC-MLI requires fewer switching instants with and one switch less in conduction path. This makes the INSC-MLI efficient than the topologies present in the recent literature. Also, the total blocking voltage of the INSC-MLI is 8 p.u which is less than the BSC7MLI [\[34\]](#) wherein the blocking voltage is 9 p.u.

6. Conclusion

A switched capacitor based multilevel inverter topology called INSC-MLI is proposed. The INSC-MLI requires only nine IGBTs to deliver 7 levels in the stair case voltage wave form with a voltage boost factor of 1.5. The Neutral point clamped capacitors are inherently balanced through proper grounding. The floating capacitors are balanced by switching them during positive and negative cycles such that the net current through the capacitors during a cycle is zero. The performance of the topology is evaluated using simulation and experimental results and found that it requires a smaller number of switches and switching instants when compared to the topologies presented in recent literature. Further it is found operating efficiently during dynamic load conditions and modulation index variations.

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